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Biochemical And Antioxidant Analysis Of *Cassia alata* linn Flower And Leaves

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ABSTRACT

Cassia alata linn is a popular medicinal plant that has been widely used for its therapeutic properties. In this study, we conducted a phytochemical screening, antimicrobial analysis and antioxidant analysis of the flower and leaves of *Cassia alata linn* using standard methods. The results showed the presence of various phytochemicals such as alkaloids, saponin, flavonoids tannins, phenols, anthraquinone, glycoside and amino acids in both the leaves and flower while coumarins and steroids were found present in the leaves only. The study further revealed that the flower and leaves of *Ccassia alata linn* significantly exhibit antimicrobial activity against some clinical isolates as well as high antioxidant activity. These findings confirms that *Cassia alata linn* has great potential for use as a remedy against some pathogens justifying its use by traditional medicine practitioners.

Keywords: Phytochemical, antioxidant, clinical isolates, antimicrobial

INTRODUCTION

Since time immemorial herbal plants have been used as a source of medicine for developing immunity or cure against cold, jaundice, fevers and many different ailments. Modern medicine has been built on what nature has offer and has drawn upon traditional systems of knowledge of how these medicinal plants, herbs, roots, and bark were wielded to cure diseases across civilizations (WHO, 2023). The scientific assessment of the pharmacological activities of herbal plants revealed more than 200,000 phytochemicals. These compounds contribute to the view of medicinal activities displayed by plants and always justify the involvement of natural products in the development of new drugs. Despite these achievements, the use of herbal drugs was not universally accepted in contemporary medicine due to lack of scientific evidence and proper documentation (Oladeji, *et al.*, 2020), hence there is a need to have a good number of research to evaluate the phytochemicals, bioactivities and antioxidant potential. It is against this background that this study is designed to evaluate the phytochemicals, bioactivities and antioxidant potential content of the leaves and flowers of *Cassia alata linn*.

Cassia alata linn (also known as *Senna alata* or the candle bush) is a medicinal herb of Leguminosae family. It is distributed in the tropical and humid regions (Oladeje *et al.*, 2020). The plant has been used traditionally as a remedy for a variety of health issues in Africa countries and many other countries in the world (Tanzania, India, and Indonesia among others). These health issues includes constipation, flu,

malaria, asthma, eyesight improvement, typhoid, diabetes, dermatosis, among others (Yon *et al.*, 2022 and Bharathi *et al.*, 2022).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Sample

The *Cassia alata linn* leaves and flower was collected from Potiskum and identified by a taxonomist in Abubakr Tafawa balewa University, Bauchi. The sample was then dried under shade and pulverized using mortar and pistil.

Solvents and Reagents

Dragendoff's reagent, Mayer's reagent, Wagner's reagent, Trioxonitrate (V) acid, Sodium hydroxide, sodium chloride, lead acetate, potassium hydroxide, EDTA, tetraoxosulphate (iv) acid, hydrochloric acid, perchloric acid, petroleum ether, Boric acid, ammonia solution, methyl red-methylene blue, ferric chloride, Silica gel, bromine water, perchloric acid, anti-bumping, Gelatine, ninhydrin, acetone, acetic anhydride, chloroform and deionized water.

Apparatus/Instruments

Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS), Fume cupboard, crucibles, volumetry flask, conical flask, test tube, oven, weighing balance, funnels, Whatmann Filter paper, pipettes, desiccator, rotary evaporator, beakers, Soxhlet extractor, Buchner funnel, hot plate, mortar and pistil

Extraction

Soxhlet extraction was employed as described by Hussain (2023) and James *et al.*, (2014). 100 grams of the sample was loaded into the thimble, which is placed inside the Soxhlet extractor chamber which mounted on the extraction flask containing a solvent. Condenser was fixed on the top of soxhlet and the setup was placed on a heating source and heating begins. The extraction was allowed to continue until colour was observed in the extractor thimble insuring complete extraction with a particular solvent. The extraction was done with ethyl acetate followed by ethanol and then water sequentially in the order of polarity. The extracts were filtered and concentrated using rotary evaporator. The concentrated crude extracts were then dried in a desiccator and then stored for further analysis.

Phytochemical Qualitative Analysis

The phytochemicals screening of the crude extracts from the leaves and flower of the *Cassia alata linn* were carried out using standard methods as described by Khalid *et al.*, (2018) and Banu and Cathrine (2015). The phytochemical screening investigate the presence or absence of alkaloid, saponins, flavonoids, tannins, phenolic compounds, coumarins, quinines, anthraquinones, steroids, cardiac glycosides and amino acid.

Alkaloid determination

To the aqueous crude dried extract, about 2M HCl was added to dissolve the residue. The mixture was then filtered and shared in three equal parts. To one part few drops of Mayer's Reagent was added. The second part was treat with Wagner's Reagent and the other with Dragendoff's Reagent. The presence of a creamy, orange and brownish precipitates respectively indicate the presence of reparative alkaloid.

Saponin determination

The presence of saponin will determined by frothing test. 0.5 g of the dry extract will be mixed with 10 ml distilled water and shake vigorously for 15 minutes and made to stay for thirty minutes. The appearance of a stable froth over 1.5 cm thick, implies saponin was present.

Flavonoid determination

About three drops of dilute sodium hydroxide was added to one ml of the aqueous extract. The appearance of an intensive yellow colour, which then turns colourless when few drops of dilute acid was added, implying that flavonoids are present.

Test for tannins

10 ml of bromine water was added to the 0.5 g aqueous extract. Decoloration of bromine water showed the presence of tannins.

Test for total phenols

About 100 mg of the crude extracts was dissolved in 15 ml of distilled water and divided into three portions.

a. Ferric chloride test

To first portion of the aqueous extract few drops of neutral 5% ferric chloride solution was added. A dark green colour indicates the presence of phenolic compound.

b. Gelatin test

To second portion of the aqueous extract, 2 ml of 1% solution of Gelatin containing 10% NaCl was added. White precipitate indicates the presence of phenolic compounds.

c. Lead acetate test

To third portion of the aqueous extract, 3 ml of 10% lead acetate solution was added. A bulky white precipitate indicates the presence of phenolic compounds.

Test of coumarins

Three drops of 1% KOH solution was added to the aqueous leaf extract. The appearance of a yellow colour implies coumarins were present.

Test of quinones

To small amount of the extract in a test tube, dilute sodium hydroxide was added. The absence red or blue-green colour implies that quinones were absent.

Test of Anthraquinones

Borntrager's test. About 10% of HCl was boiled for five minutes with 5 mg of the plant extract in a water bath, filtered and then left to cool. The same volume of CHCl_3 was added to the filtrate and then few drops of 10% ammonia. The mixture was subsequently heated, which produced not pinkish colouration which signifies the absence of anthraquinones.

Test of Steroids

To five milligram of the plant extract was added 2 ml of acetic anhydride, then few drops of concentrated sulfuric acid were slid through the side of the test tube. The appearance of a bluish-green colouration implies that steroids were present.

Test for Cardiac Glycosides, (Keller-Killian Test)

To 1 mg of the extract, 1 ml of FeCl_3 reagent (99 parts glacial acetic acid and 1 part five percent FeCl_3 mixture) will be added then few drops of concentrated H_2SO_4 was added too. The formation of a greenish-blue colouration in a minute implies the presence of cardiac glycosides.

Test for Amino acids

100 mg of the extract was dissolved in 10 ml of distilled water and filtered through Whatmann No. 1 filter paper. To 2ml of the filtrate two drops of ninhydrin solution (10 mg of ninhydrin in 200 ml of acetone) was added. Appearance of purple colour indicates the presence of amino acids.

Antimicrobial Analysis

Agar disc diffusion method was adopted as described by Hossain (2024) and Abbas, *et al.*, (2016) with some modification.

i. Test microbes

The antibacterial activity of crude extracts from the leaves and flower of *Cassia alata linn* were assessed against *Salmonella typhi*, *shigella dysentarae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureaus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *bacillus subtilis*, *Aspergillus niger* and *cadida albicans* maintained in brain heart infusion (BHI) at 20°C. 300 ml of each stock-culture was added to 3 mL of BHI broth. Overnight cultures was kept for 24 hours at 36°C ± 1°C and the purity of cultures was checked after 8 hours of incubation. After 24 hours of incubation, bacterial suspension (inoculum) were diluted with sterile physiological solution, for the diffusion tests, to 10⁸ CFU/cm³ (turbidity = McFarland barium sulfate standard 0.5).

ii. Preparation of the agar plates

The powdered agar media was mixed with water and steamed to dissolve the agar, the whole will then be sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C and subsequently allowed to cool to about 45°C (a temperature at which the agar remains molten). Some 15-20 cm³ of the molten agar media will then be poured into the sterile labeled Petri dishes and were left undisturbed until the agar sets. The plates will be the stored closed and upside down in a refrigerator at 4°C.

iii. Agar diffusion disc

Fractions of extracts were dissolved and diluted with dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)/water (H_2O) to a concentration of 200 mg/ cm³.

6 mm filter paper discs (Whatman, no. 3) were impregnated with 20 cm³ of each of the constituted extracts. The discs was allowed to remain at room temperature until complete diluent evaporation and kept under refrigeration until ready to be used. The bacterial inoculum were then be uniformly spread using sterile cotton swab on the agar in the sterile Petri dishes. Discs loaded with extracts were placed onto the surface of the agar

in the Petri dishes. Commercial Ciprofloxacin and Amphotericin B. (200 mg) were used as positive control while distilled water/DMSO were used as negative control. Tests were performed in triplicate. The disc/plates were incubated at 37°C for 48 hrs.

The microbial activities of the extracts/compounds and controls against selected bacterial strains were recorded in the form of inhibition zone and measured in millimeter with Vernier Caliper/plastic ruler.

The Student's T–test was used to compare results between the inhibition zones of the sample and that of the standard drugs. P values lower than 0.05 (p < 0.05) was considered significant.

Antioxidant Activity

In-vitro Antioxidant activity was tested using DPPH (1, 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) free radical scavenging as described by Rahman *et al.*, (2015) and Muthoni *et al.*, (2020). The hydrogen atom donating ability of the plant extractives was determined by the decolorization of methanol solution of 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH). DPPH produces violet/purple color in methanol solution and fades to shades of yellow color in the presence of antioxidants. DPPH solution (0.004%w/v) was prepared in 95 % ethanol. Two different concentrations (100 µg/cm³ and 50 µg/cm³) of extracts under study were prepared and placed in test tubes. 1 ml of freshly prepared DPPH reagent was added to each of the test tubes and incubated in dark. After 10 minutes of incubation, the absorbance was measured at 517 nm using spectrophotometer. Ethanol was used to set the absorbance zero. A blank sample containing the same amount of ethanol and DPPH was also prepared and incubated for 10 mins and then the absorbance was measured. All determinations were performed in triplicate. Free radical scavenging activities of the test sample expressed as percentage of inhibition were calculated according to the following equation.

$$\text{Percentage (\%)inhibition of DPPH activity} = \frac{AB - AA}{AB} \times 100$$

AA - absorbance value of test sample
 AB – absorbance value of blank sample.

RESULTS

Result of the Phytochemicals screening of the leaves and Flowers of the *Cassia alata linn*

The preliminary phytochemical screening of the crude extract from the leaves and flowers of *Cassia alata linn* reveals the presences of alkaloids, saponnin, flavonoids tannins, phenols, anthraquinone, glycoside and amino acids. While coumarins and steroids were found to be present the leaves and absent in the flowers. Quinones are absent in both the leaves and flowers. The summary of the screening result is shown the table 1 below.

Table 1. The phytochemical screening of the leaves and flowers of the *Cassia alata linn*

Phytochemicals screened	Leaves Extracts			Flowers Extracts		
	water	Ethanol	Ethyl acetate	water	Ethanol	Ethyl acetate
Alkaloids	+	+	-	+	+	-
Sponnin	+	+	-	+	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+	-	+	+	+
Tannin	+	+	+	+	+	+
Phenols	+	+	+	+	+	+
coumarins	+	-	-	-	-	-
Quinones	-	-	-	-	-	-
Anthraquinone	-	-	+	+	-	+
Steroid	+	+	-	-	-	-
Glycoside	+	+	+	+	+	+
Amino Acid	+	+	-	+	-	-

Key: + = Present, - = Absent

Antimicrobial analysis of the *Cassia alata linn* Leaves and Flower Extract

The antimicrobial activities of the *cassia alata linn* leaves and flower extracts were test on *Salmonella typhi*, *Shigella dysenterae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureaus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *bacillus*

subtilis, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Candida albicans*. Amphotericin B, and Ciprofloxacin were used as positive control against Fungi and Bacteria respectively while distilled water/dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) that were used in reconstituting the extracts were used as negative control. The zone of inhibition across the test sample against the microbes range from 23 mm to 02 mm while for the positive control it was 24 mm to 18. An inhibition above 08 mm is considered as significant that implies that for the leaves extract all the extract significantly inhibits growth of the test microbes with the exception of *A. niger*, *B. subtilis* and *P. aeruginosa* which shows resistance on ethyl acetate extracts and *A. niger* resist the activity of the water extract. The narrative for the activity of the flower extracts against the test microbe was similar to that of the leaves extracts. The summary of the antimicrobial analysis can be seen in table 2 below.

Table 2. Antimicrobial Analysis of the *Cassia alata linn* leaves and Flowers Extracts. (Concentration of the extracts and the control were 200 mg/ml)

Plant Parts	Microorganisms	Microorganisms				
		water	Ethanol	Ethyl acetate	cipro/amp	Distilled water/DMSO
Leaves	<i>S. typhi</i>	23	21	13	24	00
	<i>S. dysenteriae</i>	12	16	09	23	00
	<i>E. coli</i>	21	19	10	24	00
	<i>S. aureaus</i>	9	11	11	25	00
	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	10	14	03	22	00
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	16	15	07	19	00
	<i>A. niger</i>	08	12	04	18	00
	<i>C. albicans</i>	14	19	11	20	00
Flower	<i>S. typhi</i>	17	23	14	24	00
	<i>S. dysenteriae</i>	12	18	07	23	00
	<i>E. coli</i>	22	17	08	24	00
	<i>S. aureaus</i>	11	11	06	25	00
	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	09	13	02	22	00
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	14	14	07	19	00
	<i>A. niger</i>	15	13	12	18	00
	<i>C. albicans</i>	14	18	10	20	00

Keys: *S. typhi* - *Salmonella typhi*
S. dysenteriae - *shigella dysenteriae*
E. coli - *Escherichia coli*
S. aureaus - *Staphylococcus aureaus*
P. aeruginosa - *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*
B. subtilis – *bacillus subtilis*
A. niger - *Aspergillus niger*
C. albicans - *cadida albicans*
Cipro – Ciprofloxacin (antibiotics)
Amp - Amphotericin B (Antifungal)
DMSO - dimethyl sulphoxide

Antioxidant Analysis of the *Cassia alata* Leaves and Flower Extract

The antioxidant activities of the extracts shows significant inhibition (78.09 % to 71.23 %) as compared to that of ascorbic acid (control) which was 83.04 % at a concentration of 100 µg/cm³ and at concentration of 50 µg/cm³ the percentage inhibition of the test extract 72.76 % to 63.42 % compared with that of ascorbic acid (80.00 %). The summary of the result is shown in table 3 below.

Table 3. The Antioxidant Activities of the *Cassia alata linn* Leaves and Flower Extract

Sample		100 µg/cm ³ Absorbance	% inhibition	50 µg/cm ³ Absorbance	% inhibition
Leaves	Water	0.115	78.09	0.172	67.23
	Ethanol	0.143	72.76	0.189	64.00
	Ethyl acetate	0.151	71.23	0.192	63.42
Flowers	Water	0.117	77.71	0.143	72.76
	Ethanol	0.121	76.95	0.151	71.23
	Ethyl acetate	0.128	75.61	0.155	70.47
	Control	0.089	83.04	0.105	80.00
	Blank	0.525		0.525	

DISCUSSION

The study revealed that alkaloids, saponin, flavonoids tannins, phenols, anthraquinone, glycoside and amino acids present in both the *Cassia alata linn* leaves and flower of the extracts. This is in accord with Toh *et al.*, (2023) and Edegbo *et al.*, (2023) who found glycosides, anthraquinone, flavonoids, aglycons proteins, cardiac glycosides, steroids, alkaloids, phlabotannin, phenols, saponins, tannins, terpenoids, flavonoids, and carbohydrates. The study also reveals that the leaves as well as the flower extracts inhibits the test microorganisms to significant levels as compared with the control drugs indicating that the *Cassia alata linn* plant has potential as both antibiotic as well as antifungal. This agreed with Toh *et al.*, (2023) finding who observed strong inhibition of the plant extracts against *S. aureus* and other clinical isolates as well Edegbo *et al.*, (2023) who says the leaves of *cassia alata linn* has potential as an antifungal agent. The antimicrobial activities of the extract would be attributed to the numerous phytochemicals observed in both the leaves and flowers extracts. The study also reveals that the leaves and flower of *Cassia alata linn* has potential as antioxidant agent compared to ascorbic acid which would be attributed to the presence of the flavonoids, tannins and anthraquinone. This is in accord with Megawati (2024) who reported DPPH radical scavenging activities were highest in the ethyl acetate extract of *Cassia alata linn* leaves extract and Oso and Olowookere (2018) who found that *Cassia alata* leaves extracts has antioxidant properties suggest that methanol could be a perfect solvent for the extraction of antioxidant compounds from the leaves of *Cassia alata*.

CONCLUSION

The study reveals that *Cassia alata* leaves and flowers extracts contain alkaloids, saponin, flavonoids tannins, phenols, anthraquinone, glycoside coumarins, steroids and amino acids. The extracts from both samples showed strong antimicrobial and antioxidant activities. The strong antimicrobial and antioxidant activities would be attributed to the presence of the phytochemicals observed. These indicates that *Cassia alata linn* could be a source of new antibacterial, antifungal and antioxidant drugs.

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